

The science of growing and caring for plants in *Bṛhatsamhitā*

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ABSTRACT

This paper is discussing the ancient treatment of trees which has been reflected in the text of *Bṛhatsamhitā*. This text is verily associated with the *Vedas* or the knowledge of treasury. Vedas are four in numbers. In the tradition of knowledge, there are also four *Upavedas*- *Dhanurveda*, *Stāpatyaveda*, *Gāndharvaveda* and *Āyurveda*. *Upavedas* are actually known as the applied knowledge of science. These *Upavedas* are basically designed on technical work. There are so many literatures which have been composed by our ancient seers. *Śrīvarāhamihira* is the most efficient personality in the ancient science of knowledge. He has written the text of *Bṛhatsamhitā*. This is treated as the technical literature in the language of Sanskrit. There are one hundred and six chapters in this text. The chapter LV of this text is named as *Vṛkṣāyurveda* or the science of gardening. Gardening is closely associated with town-planning, house-building and construction of tanks. Ancient Sages like *Śrīvarāhmihira* has laid down rules about plantation and treatment of trees as well. The present study is an attempt to discuss the technique adopted in the science of gardening according to *Śrīvarāhamihira*.

Keywords: *Ārāma*, *Viḍaṅga*, *Sesamum*, *Vṛkṣāyurveda*, *Saṅkrāmaṇaviropanam*

0.0 Introduction

In the Science of Gardening, the technical literature *Bṛhatsamhitā*, is incredible. In this context Maharishi *Veda Vyāsa* declares:

“*Yadihāsti tadanyatra ynnehāsti na tat kvacit*”

Whatever has been said in this book, the same is everywhere, and whatever is not narrated here, is nowhere else. *Ārāma* or the science of gardening is very ancient in India. The word *Ārāma* is a sanskrit word which is derived from the root *Ram ānande* with the suffix *ghañ*. So, *Ārāma* means a suitable place for pleasure in general. Our ancient texts of knowledge are composed in such a way for peaceful living of mankind. The *Bṛhatsamhitā* stands a vital role in spreading the scientific knowledge throughout the World.

In this context trees play a vital role in the science of gardening. So, the author of *Bṛhatsamhitā* was very much conscious about the diagnosis of diseases of trees and their treatment. There are some ancient method of treatment of trees is discussed in this study. The topic like the placement of Garden, the treatment of soil, the auspicious tress for gardening, the watering of garden, Transplantation of trees are very scientific in nature. The symptoms of disease of tree, reflected in this text are very much helpful to the modern science of agriculture. The treatment of seeds is essential for plantation. The technique applied for treatment of seeds is also scientific. The present study is analyzing the very significant concept developed in the Ancient Indian Science of Gardening. The following figure is showing the detail of Ancient Indian Science and Technology.

1.0 The Nature and Scope of this study

Bṛhatsamhitā is a technical literature in Sanskrit language. This is a text of ancient Indian science and technology. The 412 B.C. is attested by Historian as the time of *Śrīvarāhamihir* the author of this text. Ancient Science and Technology is an everlasting source of intellectual resource. The nature of this study is to bridge the gap between ancient and modern science of technology. Moreover, the 21st century is expecting to carry on more research on ancient Indian science and technology. To glorify our ancient Indian scriptures, this kind of study is a primary attempt. This present study is also to create awareness towards ancient science and technology of the past and their utility in the current scenario. No doubt, there is scope for further study on the text of *Bṛhatsamhitā*.

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE PRESENT STUDY

- To create awareness among the school students about the ancient Indian scientific method for gardening.
- To incorporate our scientific culture and heritage in the syllabus of School Curriculum.
- To provide practical knowledge of gardening to the students in the school environment.
- To propagate the ethos of our ancient science and technology.
- To encourage school students to carry out small research project on ancient Indian gardening system.

2.0 The placement of Garden

The ancient word stands for garden is *ĀRĀMA* which means pleasurable. So, the pleasant as well as agreeable placement is essential to form a garden. The author has fixed the banks of waters as the best placement.

*Prāntacchāyāvinirmuktā manojñā jalāśayāḥ /
Yasmādato jalaprānteṣvārāmān viniveśayet //¹*

¹ *Bṛhatsamhitā*-1/55

The sides of rivers and lakes and other water banks will not be pleasant without shady trees. Both the Banks and gardens are mutually beneficial for human being. That is why charming gardens like the Brindavan Garden in Mysore have been created near dams and reservoirs in the modern India.

3.0 *Sesamum*-treatment for the soil

Preparation of soil for gardening is the most necessary for any kind of plantation. The author has describing about the *Sesamum*-treatment for soil.

Mr̥dvī bhūḥ sarvavr̥kṣāṇām hitā tasyām tilān vapet /

Puspitāmstāsca mṛdnyātkarmaitatprathamam bhuvah //²

A soft soil is helpful for all varieties of trees. First of all one ought to sow there *sesmum*, which must be crushed when in bloom. This is the first treatment to be done for the soil. The *sesamum* plants in bloom, when cut into pieces and allowed to mingle with the soil, would become an excellent green manure for preparing the soil for further cultivation. It is also held that if this sesamom crop does not flourish in a field, nothing could be grown there with advantage.

4.0 Trees for Initial Plantation

The author has prescribed some particular names of trees for initial stage of plantation. There are *Ariṣṭa*, *Aśoka*, *Punnāga* and *Śiriṣa* trees and *Priyaṅgu* creeper. These trees are auspicious for the garden as well as near houses.

Ariṣṭāśokapunnāgaśiriṣāḥ sapriyaṅgavaḥ /

Maṅgalyāḥ pūrvamārāme ropanīyā gr̥heṣu vā //³

These trees will bring prosperity to the human being. These names of trees are Indian botanical terms which have been highlighted in the above verse. *Ariṣṭa* is soap berry tree. It is also known as Neem Tree. *Aśoka* is a name of the tree *Jonesia Aśoka*. *Punnāga* is a name of the tree *Rottleria tinctoria*. A yellowish dye is prepared from the blossoms of this tree. *Śirisa* is a tree which has small flowers of white and fragrant. *Priyaṅgu* is a medical plant.

5.0 Grafting and Transplantation

The author has mentioned some particular names of trees for grafting and transplantation purposes. They are *Panasa*, *Aśoka*, *Plantain*, *Jāmbū*, *Lakuca*, *Dāḍima*, *Drākṣā*, *Pālivāta*, *Bijapūra* and *Atimuktaka*.

Panasāśokakadalījambūlakucadāḍimaḥ /

Drākṣāpālivatāścaiva vījapūrātimuktakaḥ //

Ete drumāḥ kāṇḍaropyāḥ gomayena pralepitāḥ /

Mūlocchede'thavā skandhe ropanīyāḥ param tataḥ//⁴

² *Bṛhatsamhitā*-2/55

³ *Bṛhatsamhitā*-3/55

⁴ *Bṛhatsamhitā*-4-5/55

Grafting may be done in respect of these trees by smearing a branch with cow dung and transplanting it on the branch of another. It may be done by cutting off the trunk of a tree and by transplanting it like a wedge on the trunk of another tree.

6.0 Period of Grafting

One should have the knowledge of the Period of grafting for gardening. The author has determined clearly the Indian period of grafting.

Ajātaśākhān śisīre jātiśikhān himāgame /

Varṣāgame ca suskandhān yathādiksthānpraropayet //⁵

In the above verses, there are three type of trees discussed for grafting. Trees that grow without branches are the first category. This type of trees must be planted in **Śisīra** season or within the month of February and March. Trees that grow with branches are the second type. This type of trees must be planted in the **Hemanta** season or within the month of December and January. The third type of trees those which have large branches or good trunk. These must be planted in the rainy season or within the month of August and September. The trees may be planted in any quarter of the garden.

7.0 Treatment of Trees during Grafting in another place

The author has mentioned the ancient method of treatment of trees which is very much significant. He used the term like **saṅkrāmaṇaviropanam** which means safety transfer of tree to another place for plantation. For this purpose, the author has prescribed a mixture of medicine for trees.

Ghṛtaśīratilakṣaudraḍangakṣīrogomyaiḥ /

Āmūlaskandhaliptānām saṅkrāmaṇaviropanam //⁶

The mixture of this medicine is a composition of ghee, **andro-pogon**, sesamum, honey, **Vidāṅga**, milk and cow-dung. Trees can be taken to other countries and there grafted on others, if they are smeared from the root of the branches with this mixture of medicine. This is called as the **Saṅkrāmaṇaviropana** growth.

8.0 Maintaining of purification during Grafting

The author has emphasized on maintaining of cleanliness during plantation. According to the author, one should be clean and pure and worship a tree with ablutions and sandal paste and then graft it. The trees will then bear the leaves of their parent trees.

Śucirbhūtvā taroḥ pūjām kṛtvā snānānulepanaiḥ /

Ropayedropitaścaiva patraistaireva jāyate //⁷

⁵ *Bṛhatsamhitā-6/55*

⁶ *Bṛhatsamhitā-7/55*

⁷ *Bṛhatsamhitā-8/55*

Our ancient scriptures are very much conscious on the purification of body as well as mind. Purity of the heart creates harmony of the mind. At the same time, maintaining of purification during plantation is necessary for the welfare of the trees.

9.0 Fixation of time for Watering

Water is nothing but the life. Watering in right time is the best treatment of trees according to the text of *Bṛhatsamhitā*. The author has provided standing time table for watering so that no tree will be destroyed.

*Sāyaṃ prātaśca gharmartau śītakāle dināntare /
Varṣāsu ca bhuvāḥ śeṣe sektavyā ropitā drumāḥ //⁸*

The transplanted trees should be watered both in the morning and evening everyday in summer. In the cold season, they should be watered in the midday or on the alternate day. In the rainy season, trees should be watered whenever the soil is found dry.

10.0 List of tree that grows in Moist soil

The author has produced a list of tree that grows in a moist soil. There are sixteen in numbers.

*Jāmbūvetāsavānīrakadambodumbarārjunāḥ /
Bījapūrakamṛdvīkā lakucāśca sadāḍimāḥ //
Vañjulo naktamālaśca tilakaḥ panasastathā /
Timiro'mrātakaśceti ṣoḍśānūpajāḥ smṛtāḥ //⁹*

The *Jāmbu*, the *Vetasā*, the *Vānīra*, the *Kadamba*, the *Udumbara*, the *Arjuna*, the *Bījapūraka*, the *Mṛdvīkā*, the *Lakuca*, the *Dāḍimā*, the *Vñjula*, the *Naktamāla*, the *Tilaka*, the *Panasa*, The *Timira* and the *Āmrātaka* are the sixteen trees that grow in a moist soil.

11.0 Fixation of distance between one tree and another in Garden

Trees that have grown quite close to one another and are touching one another with their roots interlocked are tortured. In this condition trees do not grow well. As a result, they do not yield fruits in full measure.

*Abhyāsajatāstaravaḥ saṃsprśntaḥ parasparam /
Miśrairmūlaisca na phalaṃ samyagyacchanti pīḍitāḥ //¹⁰*

Therefore, the author has fixed a distance between one tree and another in a garden. This is also very much scientific in nature. The modern technique of cultivation is giving importance about the distance between one tree and another. Maintenance of suitable distance among trees will help for easy application of modern equipments.

*Uttamaṃ viṃśatirhastā madhyamaṃ ṣoḍśāntaram /
Sthānāt sthānāntaram kāryaṃ vṛkṣāṇām dvādaśāvaram //¹¹*

According to the *Vṛhatsamhitā*, an interval of twenty cubits between trees is the best type of gardening. An interval of sixteen cubits between trees is passable and one of twelve is injurious.

12.0 Causes and Symptoms of diseases in trees

⁸ *Bṛhatsamhitā-9/55*

⁹ *Bṛhatsamhitā-10-11/55*

¹⁰ *Bṛhatsamhitā-13/55*

¹¹ *Bṛhatsamhitā-12/55*

One should have the knowledge about the causes and symptoms of diseases found generally in trees. After knowing the detail of diseases, one should start treatment of trees accordingly. Like human being, trees have also three causes of diseases. They are *Vāta* or the Wind, *Pitta* or the Bile and *Kapha* or the Phlegm in general. Trees get disease from cold weather, strong winds and hot sun.

*Śtāvātātapai rogo jāyate pāṇḍupatrātā /
Avṛddhiśca pravālānām sākhāśeṣo rasasrutīḥ //¹²*

The trees show such symptoms of disease that their leaves become pale-white, sprouts scanty and sickly, branches dry and their milk oozes out.

13.0 Treatment of Trees

The author has prescribed a simple method of treatment to trees in *Bṛhatsamhitā*. To cure the tree of these diseases, one should remove the part dead from the tree with the help of a knife. After that a paste made of *Viḍaṅga*, ghee and slit must be applied to those parts and they should be sprinkled with water and milk.

*Cikitsitamthaitēṣām śāstreṇādau viśodhanam /
Viḍaṅgaghṛtapaṅkātān secayet kṣīravāriṇā //¹³*

Viḍaṅga is a particular herb which is used as the medicinal substance for the disease of tree. The treatment through milk and water was very famous in that time.

*Phalanāśe kulatthaiśca māṣairmudgaistilairyavaiḥ /
Śṛtaśtāpayah sekaḥ phalapuṣpasamṛddhaye //¹⁴*

When the fruits of a tree are destroyed prematurely, it should be watered with milk that has been cooled after being boiled, with horse -gram, black gram, green gram, *sesamum* seeds and barley. Then the trees will yield an increase of flowers and fruits. The author has prescribed a scientific way of treatment for increasing the yield of flowers and fruits of trees, creepers and shrubs. It is mixture prepared with the following medicinal substances.

1. One āḍhaka (54Palas) of the powder of the dung of goats as well as of sheep.
2. One āḍhaka of sesamum powder.
3. A *prastha* (16 Palas) of wheat particle.
4. A *Tulā*(100Palas) of beef.
5. A *Droṇa*(256 Palas) of water.

These substances are highly medicinal according to the *Vṛkṣāyurveda*. Having the collection of all these substances, one should form a mixture. Then the mixture must be kept untouched for seven days. At the end of the seven days, it will be ready for applicable as medicine.

*Avikājaśakṛccūrṇasyāḍhake dve tilāḍhakam /
Saktuprastho jaladroṇo gomaṁsatulayā saha //
Saptarātroṣitaiḥ sekaḥ kāryo vanaspateḥ /
Vallīgulmalatānām ca phalapuṣpāya sarvadā //¹⁵*

¹² *Bṛhatsamhitā-14/55*

¹³ *Bṛhatsamhitā-15/55*

¹⁴ *Bṛhatsamhitā-16/55*

¹⁵ *Bṛhatsamhitā-17-18/55*

This mixture will be applied with water. The quantity of mixture which is said by the author is for one tree only. The quantity of substances will be increased for more trees.

14.0 Treatment of seeds

The author has described a natural treatment of seeds. The following substances are required in this treatment.

1. Milk,
2. Ghee,
3. Cow-dung,
4. Flesh of deer and hog,
5. Serum or marrow of the fish and the pig,
6. Water.

*Vāsarāṇi daśa dugdhabhāvitaṃ bījabhājyayutahastayojitaṃ /
Gomayen bahuśaḥ virūkṣitaṃ krauḍamārgapiśitaiśca dhūpitaṃ //
Māṃsasūkaravsāsamavitaṃ ropitaṃ ca parikarmitāvanau /
Kṣīrasaṃyutalajāvasecītaṃ jāyate kusumayuktameva tat //*¹⁶

The Process:

- Keep the seeds soaked in milk for ten days.
- Rubbing ghee over the hands the seed shall be taken up in the hands and passed from hand to hand till it is covered with ghee.
- They must be rolled many times in cow-dung and exposed to the smoke of the flesh of the hog and the deer.
- It shall be mixed with the serum or marrow of the fish and the pig.
- When dry, it shall be sown in well prepared soil and watered with a mixture of milk and water.
- Being sprinkled with milk and water, they will grow and bloom.

15.0 Importance of Gardening

Plantation is connected with the rain. There will be good rain in those countries where trees, shrubs and creepers grow luxuriantly with glossy leaves uninjured by worms, but if the leaves should be otherwise there will be little rain.

*Yasmin kāle snigdhanīschidrapatrāḥ sandṛśyante vṛkṣagulma latāśca /
Tasminvṛṣṭiḥ śobhanā saṃpradiṣṭā rūkṣaiśchidrairpambhaḥ pradiṣṭam //*¹⁷

This significant of gardening narrated in *Bṛhatsamhitā* is very much acceptable in the modern science of technology.

16.0 Findings of the Present Study

- Indian Botanical Science is reflected in the Text of *Bṛhatsamhitā*. The Botanical terms used by the author are significant.
- Ancient scriptures are highly emphasized on Gardening.
- The Placement of Gardening narrated by the author is relevant to the modern society.
- Fixation of distance among trees during plantation is helpful for modern agricultural science.
- The ancient method of Grafting and Transplantation will be helpful for rapid production.

¹⁶ *Bṛhatsamhitā*-19-20/55

¹⁷ *Bṛhatsamhitā*-14/29

- Maintenance of purity in body is very much necessary during any kind of plantation.
- The way of identification of symptoms of diseases in trees is very much scientific.
- The treatment of trees as well as seeds is scientific and relevant to the modern agricultural science.
- Connection of rainfall with gardening is a scientific fact described in *Bṛhatsamhitā*.

17.0 Gardening for School Science Education

The Gardening is an ancient education system. In our Indian scriptures, there are so many thoughts on the protection of trees. The child education was based on work education. Students of the Vedic period were very much interested in plantation of trees. Now days, the work education is disappeared from the school environment. In this connection, the text of *Bṛhatsamhitā* will help to start a new trend of education. The science of gardening reflected in this text is also required both for the teacher and students to initiate small project in an innovative idea. The implementation of ancient gardening system is a challenge for the Indian Educationist in the modern scenario. The ancient Indian thought on gardening is an example for the Environmental Education. To resolve the universal environmental pollution, the gardening for school science education should be welcomed in the modern society.

18.0 Discussion on Gardening as a Part of School Curriculum

Indian botanical terms can be incorporated in the school science curriculum. The Indian Students are necessary to have the knowledge about the ancient scriptures of gardening. A single chapter on the ancient gardening technology can be added in the school curriculum. Having sufficient knowledge about gardening in school environment, a student will undertake research program in higher education. Basically, a student of science stream in Higher Secondary Education will be shelf motivated to create new dimension of research program in the future. It is not necessary to create a new teaching faculty for this new syllabus. The Work Education Teachers as well as the Science Teachers are sufficient to teach such ancient technology of gardening in modern methodology of teaching. So, it is time to relook the ancient science and technology as a part of modern school curriculum.

19.0 Conclusion

The present study evident that the ancient science of gardening which was very much technical in nature. The ancient methodology for treatment of trees shall be helpful for the deep study in further research program in the area of ancient botanical science. The Indian concept of *Vṛkṣāyurveda* may be the real contribution of our ancestors to the Intellectual world of science. So, this kind of study is a primary attempt in the light of gardening. The text of *Bṛhatsamhitā* is creating the new path of research in the area of modern science of treatment of trees. Moreover, the implementation of Ancient Indian science and technology in the school science education is a greater attempt to purify the current curriculum of school students. It can be rightly said that *Naven Anavam Śodhayet* or relook the ancient sources of knowledge in modern perspective.

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